

A Framework for Automated Integration of High-Level Simulators in RISC-V SoCs

Pedro Ramalho^{1,2}, Nuno Paulino¹[0000–0001–5547–0323], and João Bispo^{1,2}[0000–0002–3017–9449]

¹ Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, Portugal

² INESC TEC, Porto, Portugal

{pedro.m.ramalho, nuno.m.paulino, joao.bispo}@inesctec.pt

Abstract. To achieve further performance and efficiency, System-on-Chip (SoC) designs increasingly rely on core customization or integration of application-specific hardware blocks. This requires extensive efforts during Design Space Exploration (DSE) of new hardware to achieve integration, correctness, and target performance. This is time-consuming and error-prone, hindering fast iterative hardware/software co-design. This paper presents a co-simulation framework which integrates arbitrary high-level simulators into Verilog-based SoC platforms, demonstrated on the RISC-V-based open-source X-HEEP SoC. Using inter-process communication we enable cycle-accurate lock-step co-simulation where high-level simulators of accelerators are exposed as memory-mapped peripherals to the RISC-V core. For experimental validation we re-implemented an existing peripheral of the X-HEEP SoC written in Register-Transfer Level (RTL) as an external simulator process, and observed that the co-simulated version maintains identical cycle-level behavior with a maximum wall-clock overhead of 11%. This work enables fast DSEs of heterogeneous RISC-V-based SoCs.

Keywords: RISC-V · Co-Simulation · Hardware acceleration · integration · design-space-exploration

1 Introduction

Modern SoCs increasingly integrate domain-specific accelerators alongside general-purpose Reduced Instruction Set Computer V (RISC-V) cores to meet the performance and energy requirements of emerging workloads. Validating these heterogeneous systems typically relies either on having RTL implementations for all components, or on co-simulation where software models and cycle-accurate RTL components execute together to expose system-level interactions before hardware fabrication. However, existing co-simulation approaches often bind designers to specific modeling languages or require extensive manual effort to connect external high-level simulators with RTL SoC platforms.

These limitations slow down prototyping and hinder fast iteration, especially when exploring alternative accelerator architectures or testing early functional

models. Furthermore, integrating new peripherals frequently demands significant boilerplate around communication interfaces, memory-mapped registers, and synchronization with the simulated SoC. To address these challenges, we propose a framework that automatically integrates high-level accelerator simulators—written in languages such as C++, Python, or Java—into a cycle-accurate RISC-V SoC simulation using Direct Programming Interface (DPI)-based inter-process communication. Our specific contributions are:

1. A declarative JSON-based flow that automatically generates all RTL stubs, DPI interfaces, and simulator templates required to integrate external accelerators.
2. A co-simulation runtime that enables bidirectional communication between Verilated RTL and high-level simulators via ZeroMQ, including support for memory transactions.
3. Validation of the approach via integration with the state-of-the-art X-HEEP SoC, showing cycle-level equivalence and less than 11% wall-clock overhead when replacing hardware accelerators with software models.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in co-simulation and accelerator integration, Section 3 presents the architecture and design of the proposed framework, Section 4 evaluates its functional accuracy and performance, and finally Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2 Related Work

We review recent notable simulation and co-simulation works in system-level simulation and hardware/software co-simulation, each targeting the challenges of accurately modeling heterogeneous SoCs and their accelerators.

GVSoc [4] is an open-source, event-driven simulator for PULP-based SoCs that targets high-speed, system-level exploration with accuracy deviations below 10%. The framework models cores, memory, Direct Memory Access (DMA) engines, and peripherals using modular C++ components, while architectural parameters such as interconnect bandwidth and latency are defined through JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) descriptions. Python generators then assemble complete platform instances from these specifications. Component interactions follow a request-based communication model, where memory requests carry address, payload, and latency information and accumulate delays as they propagate through the system. This design enables detailed performance studies without the cost of full cycle-accurate RTL simulation.

ERAS [9] addresses the difficulty of preserving signal-level accuracy when combining RTL models with higher-level, event-driven simulators. Instead of manually bridging these abstraction levels, ERAS uses ESSENT [2] to generate cycle-accurate C-models from RTL netlists, which can be loaded into architectural simulators such as SST or gem5 [11, 3]. A parser automatically produces the necessary wrapper code, creating dynamically loadable components that connect

the C-models to the simulator’s execution flow. This automation significantly reduces integration effort while maintaining accurate low-level behavior, enabling designers to perform architectural exploration without sacrificing RTL fidelity.

FLECSim-SoC [6] is a SystemC-based simulation framework for evaluating accelerators integrated into SoCs, with a focus on Deep Neural Network (DNN) co-design. The approach models Central Processing Units (CPUs), memories, and accelerators as SystemC components connected through a Transaction-Level Modeling (TLM)-based crossbar, and supports the inclusion of cycle-accurate RTL modules via Verilator. System architecture is defined in JSON files, enabling designers to vary parameters such as memory hierarchy, Dynamic Random Access Memory (DRAM) timing, and DMA behavior. The framework provides both instruction-level processor models and detailed accelerator interactions, and it integrates with energy and area estimation tools such as Accelergy [13], making it suitable for exploring hardware–software trade-offs in DNN workloads.

RoSÉ [10] is a hardware/software co-simulation infrastructure that enables closed-loop evaluation of robotics systems by coupling an environment simulator called AirSim [12] with the cycle-accurate RTL simulation framework FireSim [7]. AirSim generates sensor data and processes actuation commands at discrete time steps, while FireSim executes the target SoC at clock-cycle granularity on Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). A dedicated bridge module synchronizes the two domains by exposing memory-mapped Input/Output (I/O) registers and exchanging state information over Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). A lockstep synchronizer aligns simulation time across both engines—despite their differing time bases—ensuring that sensor updates, actuator commands, and hardware events remain coherent throughout execution. This enables realistic pre-silicon evaluations of robotics workloads with tight hardware–environment interaction fidelity.

Kwon *et al.* [8] propose a simulation framework that couples QEMU-based software emulation with real-time RTL models through a virtual interface layer. QEMU generates a JSON-described register map and is extended to forward peripheral register activity to Verilog simulations via IEEE PLI [1], while a socket-based communication module enables bidirectional data exchange and debugging over TCP. The framework supports dynamic loading of RTL modules and distributes simulation workloads across multiple hosts by segmenting models into parameterized units. This design allows embedded software to interact seamlessly with cycle-accurate hardware blocks, enabling flexible architectural exploration without modifying application code.

Busnot *et al.* [5] introduce a parallel SystemC kernel that accelerates loosely-timed TLM simulations while remaining compliant with the IEEE SystemC standard. The kernel evaluates SystemC processes concurrently on multicore hosts through a parallel scheduling mechanism that preserves atomicity and determinism, avoiding race conditions. It also supports Direct Memory Interface (DMI), allowing simulated components to access host memory directly and reducing communication overhead typical of higher-level messaging. Although loosely-timed TLM abstractions sacrifice fine-grained synchronization, they enable fast

system-level exploration, and the addition of DMI further improves performance when coupling hardware models with external software processes.

Although these frameworks improve system-level and co-simulation capabilities, they are typically bound to specific modeling environments and require manual effort to integrate new accelerator models. None provide a generic, language-agnostic way to connect external high-level simulators to a cycle-accurate RISC-V SoC. Our approach instead automates this integration through a declarative specification and DPI-based inter-process communication, enabling rapid prototyping with minimal boilerplate.

3 Co-Simulation Framework Architecture

The framework is structured around three components that work together to integrate high-level simulators into a cycle-accurate RISC-V SoC. First, the hardware platform provides the simulated SoC environment, where peripherals appear as standard memory-mapped modules connected to the processor. Second, each peripheral has an associated high-level simulator process, written in a High-Level Language (HLL), which implements all functional behavior while exchanging register values and memory requests with the SoC. Third, a code-generation flow automates integration by producing the RTL stubs, DPI interfaces, and simulator templates from a concise JSON specification.

Fig. 1. Co-simulation framework instantiated on the X-HEEP RISC-V SoC. Boilerplate code to support the co-simulation is generated from JSON configuration files. The host application executes on the simulated RISC-V core, while accelerator functionality is implemented in external high-level simulator processes.

Figure 1 shows a concrete instantiation of the proposed simulation architecture using X-HEEP, an open-source SoC implemented in SystemVerilog (SV) that integrates a RISC-V processor core, memory system (omitted), and peripheral subsystem which includes already commonly used peripheral modules such as I2C or UART (omitted). A host application is compiled and executed on the RISC-V within X-HEEP, which as a whole is simulated via Verilator. The host code interacts with peripherals using Memory-Mapped Input/Output (MMIO), among which are accelerator modules whose connection to the bus is implemented via SV wrappers which contain C-based DPI calls acting as the interface to a ZeroMQ based message passing step which connects to external processes. In summary, a RISC-V binary is executed on the simulated X-HEEP processor, while external processes implement the accelerator behavior (exemplified in Listing 1.3).

3.1 Hardware Platform Integration

The hardware platform provides the cycle-accurate SoC environment in which all co-simulated peripherals operate. In this setting, each accelerator appears to the RISC-V core as a standard memory-mapped SV module connected through MMIO. Each generated peripheral exposes two interfaces to the SoC: an MMIO register file for control and status, and a pair of Open Bus Interface (OBI) channels for issuing memory read and write transactions. Although all functional behavior is delegated to an external simulator process, the peripheral remains an ordinary RTL block. It includes clock and reset signals, address-decode logic, and an OBI-compatible master interface so the simulator can initiate memory operations through the SoC interconnect.

To bridge the SV environment with the high-level simulator, each generated peripheral’s top-level module uses DPI-C calls to route register values and memory-access results between the RTL domain and a C layer linked into the Verilated SoC simulator. Listing 1.1 shows a minimal example of an MMIO-mapped peripheral whose registers are exchanged with an external simulator.

Listing 1.1. Excerpt of the communication flow in generated SV peripheral wrappers.

```

1 // (code omitted)
2 import "DPI-C" function void communication_send(int r1, int r2);
3 import "DPI-C" function void communication_recv(int r3);
4 // DPI declarations will link with C-side simulation
5
6 always_ff @(posedge clk_i or negedge rst_ni) begin
7     if (rst_ni)
8         int signed _r3; /* temporary variable... */
9         communication_send(r1, r2, ...); /* send inputs... */
10        communication_recv(_r3); /* recv outputs... */
11        r3 <= _r3;
12    end
13 end

```

3.2 Simulator Processes

Each hardware module or accelerator instantiated in the SoC as described above, implemented as a simple RTL wrapper with DPI calls, has an associated simulator process written in C++, Python, or Java. The simulator encapsulates all functional behavior of the accelerator and executes in lock-step with the cycle-accurate RTL model of the SoC. At every cycle, the simulated SoC sends the peripheral’s MMIO-visible registers to the simulator process, and the simulator returns updated register values. As mentioned above, these exchanges pass through an intermediate abstract controller interface, which also exposes blocking read and write operations implemented in the generated base-class templates, and these correspond directly to the peripheral’s OBI master channels. Thus, the simulator may trigger memory transactions without manipulating low-level protocol signals. This design makes the simulator responsible for the entire datapath logic, including state updates, FIFO management, scheduling, and algorithmic behavior, while the hardware wrapper only forwards register values and propagates memory requests to the SoC interconnect.

One simulator process is spawned per peripheral instance, and these processes are independent. This is important for scalability, because parallel simulators can model heterogeneous accelerators or multiple copies of the same accelerator without modifying the SoC testbench. Because the simulators run in user space and communicate through ZeroMQ over DPI-C, they can be modified and recompiled independently of the Verilated SoC, which significantly reduces iteration time. Since all communication between the RTL wrapper and the simulator occurs through this DPI-C based channel which is integrated in the Verilator testbench, this facilitates implementation of future features for tracing, assertions, and debugging.

3.3 Code-Generation Flow

The code-generation flow automates all steps required to integrate a new peripheral and its simulator into the SoC environment. The entry point is a JSON specification that declares the peripheral layout. This includes the memory base address, register file, data types, directions, and any configuration parameters required by the simulator.

This JSON file is parsed into an internal data model and processed by an emitter pipeline that generates three categories of artifacts: 1) a SystemVerilog peripheral wrapper that exposes MMIO registers and DPI-C entry points, 2) a simulator project for C++, Python, or Java that includes base classes and a controller interface that abstracts OBI reads and writes, and 3) integration files for the SoC testbench such as memory map definitions and build rules. Besides generating these files, certain build files need to be updated, which the current generator also supports, when the target is the X-HEEP platform.

Listing 1.2 shows a simplified example of the JSON block used to generate the module we employ for experimental evaluation in Section 4. The snippet shows how the user specifies only the peripheral identifier, target language, memory region and register definitions.

Listing 1.2. Peripheral definitions block of replicated `simple_accelerator` example.

```

1 { "identifier": "replicated_simple_accelerator",
2   "description": "A simple accelerator",
3   "class_name": "replicated_simple_accelerator",
4   "target_language": "cpp",
5   "hardware_interface": {
6     "memory_base_address": 6000,
7     "memory_size_bytes": 100,
8     "registers": [
9       {
10        "name": "src_address",
11        "direction_to_simulator": "input",
12        "type": "logic",
13        "signed": false,
14        "width": 32,
15        "default_value": 0
16      },
17      // <... omitted other registers and OBI bus interface ...>
18    ]
19  }}

```

Based on this specification, the full SystemVerilog wrapper, DPI interface and simulator base class which inherits communication interfaces for register and OBI bus access. The developer then fills in only the domain logic, as illustrated in the shortened example of Listing 1.3.

Listing 1.3. A C++ implementation of a simple accelerator's domain-specific logic.

```

1 class simple_accelerator : public base_simple_accelerator {
2   // (code omitted)
3   std::queue<write_req> fifo;
4   simulator_state busy(const sim_data &in, sim_data &out) override {
5     /* busy method called from FSM in parent class*/
6
7     if (!fifo.empty()) { /* process write requests first */
8       auto &[addr, data] = fifo.front();
9       if (this->controller.single_write(addr, data, in, out)) {
10        fifo.pop();
11        wr_count++;
12      }
13
14      if (rd_count < this->get_data_size()) { /* start issuing reads */
15        uint32_t src_addr = this->get_src_address() + rd_count * WORD_SIZE;
16        uint32_t dst_addr = this->get_dst_address() + wr_count * WORD_SIZE;
17        int32_t v_actual = this->controller.single_read(src_addr, in, out);
18        if (v_opt.has_value()) {
19          int32_t v_filtered = v_actual > this->get_threshold()
20            ? v_actual : this->get_threshold();
21          fifo.push({dst_addr, v_filtered});
22          rd_count++;
23        }
24
25        if (fifo.empty() && /* everything has been read and written */
26            rd_count == this->get_data_size() && wr_count == this->
27            get_data_size())
28          return simulator_state::DONE;
29        return simulator_state::BUSY;
30      }
31    }
32  };

```

Table 1. Experimental setup specifications

Component	Specification
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-9400F CPU @ 2.90GHz
RAM	2x8GiB DIMM DDR4 Synchronous Unbuffered 2667 MHz
GCC/G++	11.4.0
RISC-V Toolchain	Cloned from branch "2022.01.17"
Verilator	4.210 2021-07-07 rev v4.210

The above example follows a request–response execution flow in which the simulator’s `busy()` method is invoked once per cycle. The base class handles serialization, register transfer and memory-transaction state machines, ensuring that simulator and RTL wrapper remain synchronized. Users only implement the algorithm-specific logic in the simulator.

4 Experimental Evaluation

We evaluate the proposed framework by replicating and extending an existing accelerator example from the X-HEEP SoC. This accelerator applies a threshold filter to a buffer of data and writes the filtered results to another memory location using OBI transactions. The original Intellectual Property (IP) example is written entirely in SV and resides in the X-HEEP peripheral subsystem as a memory-mapped component, with a host application controlling its execution.

We performed two experiments: (i) to verify that a co-simulated accelerator produced by our code-generation flow can reproduce the functional and cycle-level behavior of the original SystemVerilog implementation, and (ii) to measure the performance overhead introduced by the communication layer when scaling the number of accelerator instances.

The X-HEEP microcontroller was generated with default settings except for increasing the number of memory banks to 12 to support the large buffers used in our tests. All experiments run within a Verilated X-HEEP simulation using identical host software, enabling a direct comparison between the original accelerator and its co-simulated counterpart. Other hardware and software components of our experimental runs are presented in Table 1.

4.1 Experiment 1: Replicating the Simple Accelerator

Replicating the `simple_accelerator` example with our framework is a straightforward process that minimizes boilerplate and manual integration effort. The first step is to write a JSON configuration file defining the four registers used by the threshold-filter algorithm (source and destination addresses, threshold, and data size). Once the configuration file is processed, the generator produced all necessary artifacts for X-HEEP and the simulator. Namely, the SV peripheral stub for integration into the SoC and base simulator project. C++ is chosen as

Fig. 2. Single accelerator results for different data sizes implementations.

the target simulator language for this experiment. The behavior of the simulated peripheral is controlled by the host program on the RISC-V core present in the SoC, which initializes the accelerator, waits for completion, and then verifies correctness by comparing every element of the output buffer against the expected filtered values, returning the number of mismatches as the program’s exit code.

Results Figure 2(a) presents the number of clock cycles required to complete the simulation for various data sizes, comparing the original and replicated implementations. For all data sizes except the smallest one ($N = 2$), both implementations perform identically in terms of cycle count. At $N = 2$, the replicated version requires an additional 100 cycles (2102 vs. 2002). This difference in cycles probably indicates that the C++ implementation of the accelerator might be missing some edge-case. However, for every other value of N , simulation times were identical.

Figure 2(b) plots the ratio between the wall-clock times of the replicated and the original implementations. We observe a rather consistent overhead, between 6% (for $N = 2$) and 11% (for $N = 64$). Considering that the data sizes are increasing exponentially, the overhead introduced by the simulation framework appears to be constant in relation to the total simulation time.

4.2 Experiment 2: Scaling for Multiple Accelerators

The second experiment evaluates how well our framework handles simulation workloads when scaling the number of instantiated accelerators within a single system. To do this, we replicate the same accelerator used in the previous experiment and instantiate multiple copies in the same simulation environment.

Fig. 3. Single accelerator results for different number of accelerators.

This approach is used for both the original accelerator, written purely in SV, and the replicated `c++` version. We report results for configurations with 2, 4, and 8 accelerators running concurrently, all using a fixed buffer size of 256.

Results Figure 3(a) plots the growth of simulation cycles for buffer sizes of 256, using 2, 4, and 8 accelerator instances. Both implementations achieved the exact same number of simulation clock cycles. Figure 3(b) presents the ratio between the wall-clock simulation times of the two versions. The overhead remains under 10%, regardless of the number of accelerator instances. These results are generally consistent with those from the first experiment, indicating that the framework induces a constant overhead that does not grow disproportionately with the number of accelerator instances.

4.3 Analysis

In terms of simulation cycles, the only observed deviation occurred at $N = 2$, during the first experiment, where a difference of 100 cycles was recorded. While this technically disqualifies the implementation from being cycle-accurate across all cases, we believe this discrepancy stems from minor timing differences that the `c++` version did not manage to accurately capture. Given that all other tested configurations produced identical cycle counts, we are confident that the implementation remains a very close approximation of the intended behavior.

Wall-clock times for the replicated versions were consistently higher, but the overhead remained modest, reaching a maximum of around 11%. More importantly, this overhead is stable and does not increase disproportionately with the workload. Despite the exponential increase in data value, the overhead curve remains flat, indicating that the replication framework imposes a roughly constant cost rather than a scaling penalty.

Another important advantage, not reflected in these results, is the reduction in turnaround time when modifying the simulator. Unlike traditional flows that require costly regeneration and recompilation of the entire SoC simulator (for example, with Verilator), in our framework, changes to the replicated peripheral model can be tested rapidly without recompilation of the whole system. This aligns well with the framework’s goal of providing an agile prototyping and testing environment for peripherals integrated in complex systems.

It is worth noting that the accelerator used in these experiments is intentionally simple, with minimal input requirements and trivial domain logic. While this setup serves as a reasonable initial test, it may represent a worst-case scenario for co-simulation approaches where the workload is dominated by data transfer rather than computation. In such cases, higher-level implementations (for instance, in C++ or Java) may even outperform cycle-accurate RTL simulation. Therefore, further testing with more complex and computation-heavy accelerators is necessary to fully evaluate scalability and robustness.

Nonetheless, we consider that these proof-of-concept results validate the approach. Overall, the framework’s architectural overhead is manageable and consistent with the trade-offs made during design, while offering practical benefits in simulation workflow efficiency.

5 Conclusion

This work presented a co-simulation framework that integrates high-level accelerator models into cycle-accurate RISC-V SoCs through a declarative specification and automated code-generation flow. By combining generated RTL stubs, DPI-based communication, and message-oriented interaction via ZeroMQ, the approach enables high-level simulators to function as memory-mapped peripherals and autonomously issue memory transactions within a Verilated SoC environment. The experimental evaluation using the X-HEEP platform demonstrated cycle-accurate behavior, incurring at most an 11% wall-clock time overhead. These results indicate that the framework provides a practical and efficient path for rapid prototyping and iterative refinement of accelerator designs without requiring full RTL re-implementation or costly rebuilds of the entire simulation environment.

Future work will extend the experimental evaluation to more complex accelerator architectures, such as spatial arrays, as well as tightly coupled integration cases, as we have recently implemented support for co-simulation of custom instruction extensions through the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF) bus, allowing us to study instruction-level acceleration and realistic application workloads beyond memory-mapped peripherals.

Acknowledgments. This work has received funding within the Chips Joint Undertaking (Chips JU) - the Public-Private Partnership for research, development and innovation under Horizon Europe – and National Authorities under grant agreement 101096658.

References

1. IEEE Standard for Verilog Hardware Description Language. IEEE Std 1364-2005 (Revision of IEEE Std 1364-2001) pp. 1–590 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2006.99495>
2. Beamer, S., Donofrio, D.: Efficiently Exploiting Low Activity Factors to Accelerate RTL Simulation. In: 2020 57th ACM/IEEE Design Automation Conference (DAC). pp. 1–6 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/DAC18072.2020.9218632>
3. Binkert, N., Beckmann, B., Black, G., Reinhardt, S.K., Saidi, A., Basu, A., Hestness, J., Hower, D.R., Krishna, T., Sardashti, S., Sen, R., Sewell, K., Shoaib, M., Vaish, N., Hill, M.D., Wood, D.A.: The gem5 simulator. SIGARCH Comput. Archit. News **39**(2), 1–7 (Aug 2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2024716.2024718>
4. Bruschi, N., Haugou, G., Tagliavini, G., Conti, F., Benini, L., Rossi, D.: GVSoC: A Highly Configurable, Fast and Accurate Full-Platform Simulator for RISC-V based IoT Processors. In: 2021 IEEE 39th International Conference on Computer Design (ICCD). pp. 409–416. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCD53106.2021.00071>
5. Busnot, G., Sassolas, T., Ventroux, N., Moy, M.: Standard-compliant Parallel SystemC simulation of Loosely-Timed Transaction Level Models. In: Proceedings of the Asia and South Pacific Design Automation Conference, ASP-DAC. vol. 2020-January, pp. 363–368. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASP-DAC47756.2020.9045568>
6. Hotfilter, T., Hofer, J., Kreß, F., Kempf, F., Becker, J.: FLECSim-SoC: A Flexible End-to-End Co-Design Simulation Framework for System on Chips. In: 2021 IEEE 34th International System-on-Chip Conference (SOCC). pp. 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SOCC52499.2021.9739212>
7. Karandikar, S., Mao, H., Kim, D., Biancolin, D., Amid, A., Lee, D., Pemberton, N., Amaro, E., Schmidt, C., Chopra, A., Huang, Q., Kovacs, K., Nikolic, B., Katz, R., Bachrach, J., Asanovic, K.: FireSim: FPGA-Accelerated Cycle-Exact Scale-Out System Simulation in the Public Cloud. In: 2018 ACM/IEEE 45th Annual International Symposium on Computer Architecture (ISCA). pp. 29–42 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCA.2018.00014>
8. Kwon, J., Oh, S., Park, D.: Metamorphic edge processor simulation framework using flexible runtime partial replacement of software-embedded verilog RTL models. In: Proceedings - IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems. vol. 2021-May. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAS51556.2021.9401354>
9. Nema, S., Chunduru, S.K., Kodigal, C., Voskuilen, G., Rodrigues, A.F., Hemmert, S., Feinberg, B., Lee, H., Awad, A., Hughes, C.: ERAS: A Flexible and Scalable Framework for Seamless Integration of RTL Models with Structural Simulation Toolkit. In: Proceedings - 2023 IEEE International Symposium on Workload Characterization, IISWC 2023. pp. 196–200. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IISWC59245.2023.00038>
10. Nikiforov, D., Dong, S.C., Zhang, C.L., Kim, S., Nikolic, B., Shao, Y.S.: RoSÉ: A Hardware-Software Co-Simulation Infrastructure Enabling Pre-Silicon Full-Stack Robotics SoC Evaluation (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3579371.3589099>
11. Rodrigues, A.F., Hemmert, K.S., Barrett, B.W., Kersey, C., Oldfield, R., Weston, M., Risen, R., Cook, J., Rosenfeld, P., Cooper-Balis, E., Jacob, B.: The structural simulation toolkit **38**(4), 37–42 (Mar 2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1964218.1964225>

12. Shah, S., Dey, D., Lovett, C., Kapoor, A.: Airsim: High-fidelity visual and physical simulation for autonomous vehicles. In: Field and service robotics: Results of the 11th international conference. pp. 621–635. Springer (2017)
13. Wu, Y.N., Emer, J.S., Sze, V.: Accelergy: An Architecture-Level Energy Estimation Methodology for Accelerator Designs. In: 2019 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Computer-Aided Design (ICCAD). pp. 1–8 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCAD45719.2019.8942149>